

PUBLIC OPINION AND PUBLIC FOREST MANAGEMENT POLICIES IN THE CONTEXT OF COVID-19

Author(s)*: Iulian Alexandru BRATU ¹, Lucian DINCĂ ²
Position: Assist. Prof., PhD, Eng.¹, PhD, Eng.²
University: Lucian Blaga University of Sibiu
Address: Sibiu, Victoriei Str., No. 10, Romania
Email: iulian.bratu@ulbsibiu.ro ¹, dinka.lucian@gmail.com ²
Webpage: <http://www.ulbsibiu.ro/>

Abstract

Purpose – *The research aims to establish whether there is a link between civil society concerns and public policies adopted in the context of the social distance generated by the COVID-19 epidemic.*

Methodology/approach - *The present study analyzed on the one hand the press reports on deforestation, the activity of emblematic NGOs in the fight against deforestation, the messages promoted by personalities of the society (actors, musicians, journalists), petitions promoted in the virtual space, but also the environment ministry's and parliament's agenda by adopting regulations governing the field of forests.*

Findings – *The environmental protection authority promotes forestry policies and strategies that take into account both the demands of civil society and the needs of the forestry sector. There is another actor in this whole complex equation, certain politicians who, for populist purposes, promote legislative acts.*

Research limitations/implications – *The research considers the interaction between the public authority and the society through the prism of the social networks.*

Practical implications – *The research results can be used as a predictor of the evolutions of future forest management policies and strategies.*

Originality/value – *The present study analyzes the potential of social networks regarding the setting of the public agenda of the authorities.*

Key words: *deforestation, public forest policies, social networks.*

Introduction

Management is a set of techniques used to lead, manage, guide. Like any activity, it can be brought to the level of art, of perfection in leadership. Forest management refers to the organization and coordination of specific activities at the temporal, spatial and micro-economic level by hierarchically organized institutions, starting from practicing foresters, landscapers, public authority and the state (Nichiforel, 2019). In the forestry sector, management involves the administration and management of forests and "all technical, economic and legal activities carried out by public or private forestry authorities, in order to comply with forestry laws, in compliance with the forestry regime" (Law 46, 2008).

Forest management strategies are embodied in forest policies. Between 2013 and 2020, forestry policies have been regulated at EU level by the Commission "A new EU strategy for forests and the forestry sector" (COM, 2013). It set out the Union's new strategy and proposed a European reference framework for the development of sectoral policies that have an impact on forests. This strategy has two main objectives: 1) to ensure that Europe's forests are managed sustainably and 2) to strengthen the Union's contribution to promoting sustainable forest management and combating deforestation worldwide (U.E., 2020). The key directions so far this year have been sustainable management and combating deforestation.

Since 2021, forestry strategies have identified forests as one of the key areas for action to combat climate change (COM, 2019). Policy is including specific actions focus on European sources of funding

for forests, regulation of timber trade, forest biomass. The direction of European forestry strategies goes towards good forest governance, sustainable forest management and protection.

Stakeholders (De Meo, 2018) on forest policies are grouped around forest workers, civil society, politicians, environmental activists. Stakeholders in forestry tend to polarize and form opposing camps. Most forest managers and owners are aware and comply with legal requirements, however, the appreciation of the environment seems to be strongly affected by the degree of restrictions faced, being often perceived as excessive (Brukas, 2018). The divergence of interests and approaches between stakeholders lead to the idea of the need for a common language, in which there are various priorities and concerns (Ugolini, 2018). It is a positive correlation between stakeholder pressures and implementation of environmental management practices (Sarkis et al., 2010).

The period of emergency triggered by the pandemic determined the restructuring of the activity at economic and social level, through a sudden COVID-19 outbreak. There were problems related to business stability, management of daily tasks (telework or classic), increased employee stress, difficult hiring and layoffs, difficult collaboration between employees, performance parameters were difficult to achieve, the impossibility of travel. The interaction time of people with the devices has increased (Bratu, 2018b), the one related to social interactions has decreased. At the individual level, there were problems related to anxiety, depression and stress. People focused their attention on social aspects that give a meaning to existence (promotion of safety measures, environmental protection). From a psychological point of view, the individual mental balance is achieved when, against the background of a strong individual devaluation, caused by the lack of career meaning, the obligation to create a new life for children, new household occupations, there is a higher meaning of life involving present generations and future - the forest, as a source of life and vital energy (Bratu, 2019b). The well-being (Bratu, 2018a; Bratu, 2019a) that the public feels when militating for superior causes is often speculated politically; it is pleasant to be part of a national movement for good and beauty, but often they remain utopian ideals and the mass becomes a unit that can be easily manipulated.

The pages on the social networks of environmental NGOs and some personalities were analyzed, as well as the draft normative acts on the agenda of the Ministry of Environment and the Parliament, as well as normative acts published in the Official Gazette of Romania. Also, official statement of the Romanian Government were consulted regarding the environmental regulations, as well as the economic activity of the forestry sector.

It is found that during the pandemic, the activity in the online environment, especially on social networks, is much more intense. This activity corresponds to the need of society to inform and interact. Information is taken from international organizations, but also messages from environmental activists. At the same time, on the part of those who work in the forestry field, the activity of the groups has intensified, even new groups appearing that aim to counterbalance the activity of the environmental groups. Finally, with the lifting of the restrictions on the state of emergency, some environmental activists resumed their physical activity, bringing arguments in their case, arguments documented in the field. At the same time, due to the COVID-19 pandemic, there was a reduction of activity in the forest economy.

Following the Presidential Decree 195 of 16.03.2020 regarding the establishment of the state of emergency on the Romanian territory published in the Official Gazette no. 212 of 16.03.2020, the activity in almost all economic branches was suspended or drastically reduced. Prior to the Presidential Decree, large campaigns were launched announced by the Ministry of Environment, so that on March 6, the Launch of the National Afforestation Campaign "A forest as a country" was announced, on the afforestation site in Uliești, Dâmbovița County (Romanian Government, 2020c). Following the establishment of the state of emergency and the recommendations of the sanitary authorities, on March 20, on the social networks, the Ministry of Environment announces the suspension of the campaign regarding the planting of volunteers.

Material and methods

In the present study was analyzed mainly the activity on the social networks of the Public Authority for Environment, Waters and Forests during the state of emergency triggered by the COVID pandemic 19.

It is found that the social network Facebook is one of the strongest communication channels of environmental authorities, which is why the present study aimed to analyze the activity during the emergency.

The posts of the Ministry of Environment, Waters and Forests were analyzed between March 16 and May 15, 2020, in terms of total number of announcements, number of announcements related to forests, public reaction to these posts, number of comments, number of distributions, and in case of videos, number of views. Following the analysis of the announcements of the environmental authority, the impact was followed, respectively if there is a correlation between the public pressure and the legislative initiatives promoted by the authorities. The study took into account only those posts that focused on the forest.

The analyzed data were organized in the form of a database, having the following structure:

Table 1. Database structure

Article	Type
Post data	Data
COVID 19 subject	Boolean
Subject of post	Text
Forest subject	Boolean
Interacts	Number
Comments	Number
Sharing	Number
Video visualization	Number
Law impact	Text

Results and discussion

During the analyzed period, it is found that the environmental authority posted a number of 214 announcements, of which 69 had as subject the forest. Of these, the total number of interactions was 14,273, with an average of 209 interactions per post. Extracting the abnormally high values, values that we will treat separately, the average was 156 interactions at each post. The total number of comments was 10859, and extracting the maximum values of the three posts, the average is 85 comments per post. The postings had a number of 12,431 distributions, and except for the three posts, the average is 99 distributions. Out of the total number of posts, 4 of them had the effect of initiatives for legislative changes, and the post of April 1 announces the amendment of a normative act by Ministerial Order. The latter act brings stricter clarifications and regulates the activity of economic operators that carry out logging. Of the four posts, one promotes public access to the forest, and the three promote the concept that 75% of the forest area in national parks is strictly protected.

The page of the Ministry of Environment, Waters and Forests took over topics and posts of some agencies and organizations, thus 4 messages of the National Forests Authority are taken over, and one post of the Brasov Forest Guard, NGO Kogayon, Ministry of Interior, Piatra Craiului National Park; WWF Romania.

Posts that incorporated video sections provided a total number of views. Of these, two topics stand out, namely: an interview of the minister and a film related to wind gusts, each bringing 1.6 million views.

The topics that attracted the most reactions were the following:

Table 2. Top 10 topics after reactions

Subject	Reacts	Comments	Share	Movie views
Wind-uprooted trees	1.7k	2.0k	3.1k	1.6 mil
Press statements	1.3k	1.8k	1.6k	1.6 mil
Live	1.1k	1.6k	1.3k	232k
Wood transport control	567	291	621	
Proposal for strict protection of 75% of the National Parks area	423	572	278	194k
Wood traceability software (SUMAL)	411	292	476	
Planting trees	403	104	125	
Fake-news	370	151	593	
Import of wood timber	363	314	341	
Landslide	357	282	408	

The most distributed topics are listed in the table below.

Tab. 3. Top 10 topics after sharing

Subject	Reacts	Comments	Share	Movie views
Wind-uprooted trees	1.7k	2.0k	3.1k	1.6 mil
Press statements	1.3k	1.8k	1.6k	1.6 mil
Live	1.1k	1.6k	1.3k	232k
Wood transport control	567	291	621	
Fake-news	370	151	593	
Wood traceability software (SUMAL)	411	292	476	
Landslide	357	282	408	
International Forest Day	209	15	381	
Wind-uprooted trees	298	377	342	82k
Import of wood timber	363	314	341	

The topic that garnered the most reactions, comments and distributions was Wind-uprooted trees. During the analyzed period, the subject that gathered the most reactions in correlation with the COVID 19 pandemic is related to Wood transport control.

The posts that led to legislative proposals garnered 900 reactions, 726 comments and 408 distributions.

It is observed that there is a correlation between the number of reactions, the number of comments and the number of distributions. It should be noted that, in general, the most distributed posts have the highest number of reactions. However, the number of distributions is, in most cases, higher than the number of reactions or comments.

Conclusions

During the COVID 19 pandemic, the role of social networks increased in terms of information transmission, and to some extent was one of the few means of public consultation. The large number of viewers of the video content (3,432 million the first three views) leads us to believe that the subject of forest protection does not remain without echo. Perhaps, among the most visible effects of the interaction on social networks, it is the modification of normative acts that have a major impact on society. It is noted the adoption of an Order on the tightening of sanctions for deviations of economic operators (Romanian Government, 2020b), the adoption of a Decision on the operationalization of Wood traceability software (SUMAL) (Romanian Government, 2020a), and the initiation of the amendment of the Forestry Code.

We can conclude that social networks play a priority role in setting the public agenda, in adopting forest management policies.

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